

Contextualizing Instructional Strategies of High School Teachers Based on Teachers' Perceptions, Practices, and Challenges

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Publication Date: October 19, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17567862

Abstract

This study explored how high school teachers of Arellano University – Jose Rizal High School apply contextualized instructional strategies based on their perceptions, practices, challenges, and solutions, with a used of mixed-methods descriptive-correlational design. The data was gathered from 207 teachers through surveys and open-ended questions. The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Two-Way ANOVA, and Pearson correlation using

SPSS, while qualitative responses were thematically analyzed.

Findings revealed that high school teachers have a strong level of application of contextualized instructional strategies in terms of perceptions and practices, especially in connecting lessons to real-life experiences that help them make learning more meaningful and engaging. However, integrating local culture, indigenous knowledge, and community engagement remains a challenge for many teachers. The results of the

Two-Way ANOVA showed no significant differences in teachers' perceptions when grouped by educational attainment and years of service, which indicates that positive views of contextualization were shaped across teachers' demographics. In terms of a significant relationship, researchers also found a very strong positive correlation ($r = 0.903$, $p < 0.001$) between teachers' practices and the frequency of implementation, indicating that teachers who value contextualized strategies tend to use them consistently.

High school teachers experienced challenges despite positive perceptions in the implementation, such as learner diversity, lack of training and preparation, time and workload

constraints, resource limitations, and subject-specific difficulties. To address these concerns, teachers recommended the need for a stronger administrative support through professional development, provision of resources, and collaboration with colleagues that sustain the improvement of contextualized instructional strategies. Overall, the study concludes that teachers are strongly committed to contextualized instructional strategies, but they need support to sustain the implementation effectively. With that, a School Professional Development Program (SPDP) was suggested and developed for the school administrators to improve teachers' implementation of contextualized instructional strategies.

Keywords: *contextualized Instructional Strategies, perceptions, practices, challenges, solutions, professional development*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The enjoyment of teaching and learning occurs when all classroom participants have a shared opportunity to engage in the educational process. Pedroso et al. (2023) noted that contextualized teaching strategies are "instructional approaches that connect learning to a particular environment, situation, or area of application to focus on skills and support students' learning." Contextualized instructional strategies are paramount to effective education, especially in terms of enacting international practices in local contexts. However, because of the increasing diversity within the student population, adapting to an implemented approach that includes an international teaching context presents a problem since they typically lack contextualization with the students' local environment (Ma, 2025). This indicates that contextualization can become an issue in schools when importing instructional strategies without experience in the real world.

Many international studies examining contextualized instructions have explored its use as a helpful approach in classrooms. In reality, the available potential for contextualized instruction is organized, yet the challenges continue to occur at a functional level. Denu et al. (2020) determined that contextualized grammar instruction can improve students' writing abilities and their motivation to write; however, a brief intervention window period, a limited number of participants, and an overly narrow focus on writing paragraphs were the limitations. Similarly, Wickersham et al. (2022) identified that many college mathematics instructors claim they already utilize approaches to contextualize concepts, especially in-depth and more systematic contexts but experience barriers (institutional restrictions in terms of time and resources).

Additionally, Tica-a and Wangdali (2023) mentioned that to successfully contextualize instructions, teachers must design activities pertinent to students' experiences, or introduce local literature, or use students' culture, or discuss what is known within indigenous knowledges. However, teachers will face barriers to implementation, such as lack of contextualized materials or lack of knowledge of local literature and culture. Similarly, Calo (2025) identified lack of academic resources and lack of teacher support as impediments in the successful implementation of contextualized pedagogy. As such, they created a manual and a website to support teachers in the implementation process of a contextualized pedagogy in secondary mathematics classrooms.

One of the most identifiable features of the K to 12 curriculum is the implementation of instruction through contextualization and localization. Specifically, Section 10.2 of the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of Republic Act (RA) 10533 states: "Curriculum shall be contextualized and flexible enough to enable and allow schools to localize and enhance the curriculum taking into account their respective contexts of education and their social context." In order to implement contextualization and localization efficiently and effectively in all learning areas, both public and private schools, under the authority of the DepEd organized the workshop mandated strategies and created contextualize learning resources.

According to Pedroso et al. (2023), elementary teachers in Ilo-Ilo make instruction relevant for Indigenous Peoples (IP) learners by using local resources (e.g., contextualized storybooks, modules, and reading materials) and a "glocal" approach, incorporating springboard activities, differentiated instruction, one-to-one time, and equity teaching pedagogies as culturally relevant methods to engage learners. In the Southern Philippines, Diago and Dillo (2022) stated that Filipino mathematics teachers contextualized instruction by connecting lessons to students' real-life experiences, embedding cultural and indigenous competencies and practices in instruction, designing contextualized word problems, utilizing locally available or culturally observe materials as manipulatives, developing mother-tongue explanations, and applying project-based approaches to mathematics. On the other hand, public school secondary teachers in Central Philippines contextualize the English curriculum by integrating cultural references, using learners' daily experiences, adapting instructional materials, employing language bridging strategies, designing contextualized assessments, and implementing project-based activities connected to students' communities (Pariscal et al., 2022). Correspondingly, Filipino teachers contextualize social studies by localizing content, integrating learners' experiences, using current events, incorporating indigenous knowledge, employing the mother tongue, and applying collaborative strategies (Asanza, 2025).

Contextualized instructional strategies revealed that Filipino teachers frequently incorporate local culture and indigenous knowledge, link lessons to learners' real-life experiences, use localized resources and materials, explain in the mother tongue, and use collaborative or activity-based approaches to make learning more relevant and engaging. However, studies reveal common challenges faced by teachers, such as difficulties in effectively integrating local culture and indigenous knowledge, limited access to localized resources and materials, struggles in consistently connecting lessons to learners' real-life experiences, language barriers when using the mother tongue, and constraints in maintaining collaborative or activity-based approaches (Pedroso et al., 2023; Tica-a & Wangdali, 2023; Diago & Dillo, 2022; Asanza, 2025).

The Arellano University-Jose Rizal High School is an institution in the Philippines that aims to address the challenges of contextualizing instructional strategies. In fact, the school's community development reflected its mission and contextualized and culturally embedded programs that engage students in the local context. Despite the implementation of that program, Arellano University teachers could still experience the challenges due to the large classroom size, and considering the students' demographic, contextualized instructional strategies may not be ideal for the diverse students with varied

needs. Although this strategy could address a lack of student engagement, teachers were given a limited time for preparation and resources to contextualize lessons. On the other hand, teachers' backgrounds, such as age, years of service, and educational attainment, have a substantial impact on how they handle contextualization in classroom instruction and assessment. (Guadalupe, 2024). This highlighted that contextualization is more than just a pedagogy, it's also about the capacity of the teachers shaped by their personal and professional background. In the case of the school, novice teachers may struggle with contextualization due to limited exposure to diverse teaching contexts, whereas more experienced teachers may have established strategies but could also face challenges adapting to new curricula or innovations. This gap makes it necessary to pursue further investigation and should not be viewed as a barrier, but rather as a sign of where targeted capacity building and support programs should be focused.

Despite the growing recognition of contextualized instructional strategies as methods for enhancing learning experiences to be more relevant and engaging, teachers at Arellano University are still experiencing many difficulties implementing their use in instructional strategies. With this in mind, the researchers would like to investigate teachers' perceptions, practices, challenges, and possible solutions while using contextualized instructional strategies, to gain insight into how pedagogical practices can be adapted to the needs of students with different needs and apply them to a School Professional Development Program (SPDP) for teachers.

Review of Related Literature

Contextualized instruction has become a topic of interest in educational reforms, specifically, in the Philippine K-12 Curriculum and the recently implemented MATATAG Curriculum, both of which stress learner-centered and culturally responsive pedagogies. Contextualization is explained as the process of linking lesson content to learners' prior experiences, culture, and daily lives, thus increasing the relevance and engagement of the instruction (DepEd, 2016). Research indicates contextualization contributes to learning, motivation, and retention rates because it connects ideas in the classroom to students' everyday life experiences (Cabansag, 2020). In fact, researchers such as Berns and Erickson (2021) state that contextualized teaching enhances students' problem-solving skills and formalizes learning by placing knowledge within real-life contexts in their research around the globe.

Teachers' attitudes play a large role in influencing their pedagogies in the classroom. Specifically, if teachers consider contextualized instruction to be effective and beneficial, they will likely implement it at a stable rate (Yazon et al., 2020). Ocampo and Macayan (2022) found that, for example, Filipino teachers are likely to see contextualization as a necessary way to respond to diverse learning needs and students, particularly in multilingual and multicultural classroom settings. Furthermore, research outside of the Philippines highlights that contextualized practices can improve learner engagement and participation when students' local cultures and languages are in large part foundational (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 2021). Such findings imply that a positive disposition is commonly preceded by acting purposefully in one's pedagogy.

Practically, contextualized teaching happens in various ways including local texts, culture, meaningful application, and activity-based teaching. The literature shows that contextualization may improve engagement and critical thinking when lessons are linked to students' context and experience (Reyes & de Guzman, 2021), but implementation by teachers depends on resource availability, teacher development, and administrative support. For instance, a qualitative study by Tupas and Martin (2020) demonstrated Filipino educators' tendencies to practice mother tongue-based teaching, but they struggled to sustain its use because of language challenges and limited instructional resources. In addition, other

studies from around the world have shown when there is no formal support from the education system, practices of contextualized teaching are not sustainable (Leung, 2021).

Despite its benefits, contextualization has challenges. Teachers report a lack of time, contextualized resources, or professional support have all been identified as large barriers (Bautista & Dizon, 2022). Large proportions of students and diverse learning needs complicate the idea of individualized instruction (Gonzales, 2021). The same factors emerge across the world, with educators asking how to meet the demands of the curriculum and implement localized instruction (King, 2019). These constraints emphasize the need for both capacity and system-level support in order to unleash some of the potential from contextualized teaching.

In conclusion, scholars show that contextualized learning is generally understood and accepted as an effective practice to improve teaching and learning. However, its success is determined largely by teacher perceptions, their strategies, and whether their system meets their needs to support the challenges they face.

Theoretical Framework

This research is grounded on Constructivist Learning Theory of Lev Vygotsky and Culturally Relevant Pedagogy (CRP) of Gloria Ladson-Billings.

Constructivist Learning Theory, as proposed by Vygotsky, emphasizes that students actively create knowledge in interaction with their social context and environment. Contextualized teaching adheres to this idea of situating lessons within students' everyday life and culture. This theory highlights teachers' practices of situating content in authentic practices, using collaborative approaches, and scaffolding learning depending upon student needs for the purposes of this research.

Simultaneously, Culturally Relevant Pedagogy (CRP) posits that effective teaching should effectively utilize students' cultural knowledge, experience, and identity in practice as a means of facilitating academic success and critical consciousness (Ladson-Billings, 2021). This model relates to educators' attitudes and issues related to contextualization as it emphasizes the importance of recognizing students' diversity and issues related to various barriers, such as language, inclusiveness, and institutional support. Engaging CRP allows educators to navigate the challenges of contextualized practice while achieving equity in education.

Together, these two theories form the basis for the examination of how teachers feel, act, and tackle challenges in contextualizing learning in Junior High School and Senior High School levels.

Statement of the Problem

This research examines the level of application of Junior High School and Senior High School teachers' perceptions and practices about contextualizing instruction. Also, to determine the challenges and possible solutions in implementing contextualized instruction in the classroom as a basis for the School Professional Development Program (SPDP) for teachers.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

- 1) What is the level of application of High School teachers about contextualized instructional strategies in terms of:
 - a. Perceptions; and
 - b. Practices?
- 2) Is there a significant difference in High School teachers' perception of contextualized instructional strategies when grouped according to educational attainment and years of service?
- 3) Is there a significant relationship between High School teachers' practice of contextualized instructional strategies and the frequency of their instructional implementation?
- 4) What are the challenges encountered by High School teachers in implementing contextualized instructional strategies in the classroom?
- 5) What possible solutions do the respondents suggest to address these challenges and help them perform better in their field?

Null Hypotheses (H₀):

- There is no significant difference in High School teachers' perception of contextualized instructional strategies when grouped according to educational attainment and years of service.
- There is no significant relationship in practice of contextualized instructional strategies among High School teachers and the frequency of implementing instructional management.

METHODS

Research Design

This study used a mixed-methods descriptive–correlational design to better understand how high school teachers' perceptions and practices contextualized instructional strategies, while open-ended questions gave them responses to describe their challenges encountered and possible support or solutions. As stated by Esparza et al. (2023), quantitative data were analyzed with descriptive statistics, while the qualitative responses were thematically analyzed to determine teachers' experiences. This approach that combines quantitative and qualitative data provides depth understanding of teachers' instructional perceptions and practices.

Respondents and Sampling Technique

The respondents of this study were the entire population, which consisted two hundred and seven (207) High School teachers of Arellano University – Jose Rizal High School for the School year 2024-2025. The researchers utilized a total population sampling technique, which means that all teachers in the school were included. As stated by Etikan and Bala (2023), this approach is appropriate since the total number of teachers is manageable, and it ensures that the data collected represents the full range of teachers' perceptions, practices, challenges, and possible solutions in implementing contextualized instructional strategies.

Research Instruments

The main instrument used in this study was a structured questionnaire designed by the researchers to gather data on the perceptions, practices, frequency of implementation, challenges encountered, and possible solutions of High School teachers in contextualizing instruction. This questionnaire was divided into four parts: demographic profile, perceptions and practices using a five-point Likert scale, frequency of implementation, and open-ended questions on challenges and possible solutions. The items were constructed based on the review of related studies and literature to ensure alignment with the research objectives.

To establish validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by content experts, and revisions were made based on their feedback. After approval from the school administrators, the questionnaire was administered to all JHS and SHS teachers using a total population sampling technique via google Forms. Respondents were assured of confidentiality, and all retrieved data were encoded, tallied, and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. In order to determine the demographic profile of teacher-respondents, frequency and percentages were computed. The level of perceptions and practices of teachers was analyzed using the weighted mean, and standard deviation, with interpretation based on a five-point Likert scale.

To analyze the challenges and possible solutions suggested by teachers, qualitative responses from open-ended questions were examined through thematic analysis to supplement quantitative data. For the test of difference, Two-Way ANOVA using SPSS were employed to determine whether there were significant differences in the practices of contextualized instruction when teachers were grouped according to their educational attainment and years of service. Furthermore, the Pearson Correlation (r) was used to determine the relationship between teachers' practices of contextualized instruction and frequency of implementing instructional management. The level of significance was set at 0.05 alpha to guide the acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses.

Scoring of Data

5-point numerical scales with qualitative descriptive of each item and are was employed as follows:

Level of High School Teachers' Perceptions about Contextualized Instructional Strategies		
Numerical Scale	Statistical Limit	Verbal Description
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)
3	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral (N)
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)

1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)
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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Level of High Teachers’ Perceptions and Practices about Contextualized Instructional Strategies

Level of High School Teachers’ Practices about Contextualized Instructional Strategies		
Numerical Scale	Statistical Limit	Verbal Description
5	4.21 – 5.00	Always
4	3.41 – 4.20	Often
3	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes
2	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely
1	1.00 – 1.80	Never

Table 1.1. Level of High School Teachers’ Perceptions

Level of High School Teachers’ Perceptions about Contextualized Instructional Strategies	M	SD	I
1. I believe contextualized instructional strategies make learning more relevant, meaningful, and engaging.	4.45	0.99	SA
2. I believe contextualized instructional strategies help bridge learners’ experiences with lesson content.	4.54	0.88	SA
3. I believe contextualized instructional strategies address the diverse needs of learners.	4.44	0.90	SA
4. I believe contextualized instructional strategies that integrate local culture and indigenous knowledge into lessons enhance students' understanding.	4.42	0.93	SA
5. I believe contextualized instructional strategies increase student motivation and participation in the classroom.	4.49	0.91	SA
6. I believe contextualized instructional strategies are an effective way to address the diverse needs of learners in the classroom.	4.47	0.88	SA

7. I believe contextualized instructional strategies help students to develop 21 st -century skills (critical thinking, problem solving, collaboration).	4.43	0.97	SA
8. I believed contextualized instructional strategies promote a learner-centered environment rather than a teacher-centered teaching.	4.48	0.86	SA
9. I believe contextualized instructional strategies contribute to better student performance and achievement in the class.	4.46	0.92	SA
10. I believe contextualized instructional strategies strengthen the link between classroom lessons and community issues.	4.45	0.96	SA
OVERALL MEAN		4.47	SA

The results showed that teachers strongly agree on the level of perceptions about contextualized instructional strategies, with an overall mean of 4.47. The highest weighted mean of 4.54 was “contextualized instructional strategies help bridge learners’ experiences with lesson content”. However, the lowest weighted mean of 4.42 was “contextualized instructional strategies integrate local culture and indigenous knowledge to enhance students’ understanding”. Overall, teachers positively value contextualization, especially in bridging lessons with students’ experiences, but also reveal more challenging areas, such as embedding culture and indigenous knowledge.

These findings were reflected in the theory of Vygotsky’s constructivism, which emphasizes that learning is most effective when linked to students’ experiences. On the other hand, integrating knowledge was related to the study of Diago and Dillo (2022). They noted that teachers often find it difficult to integrate local or indigenous content in a subject like Mathematics and Science.

Table 1.2 Level of High School Teachers’ Practices

Level of High School Teachers’ Practices about Contextualized Instructional Strategies	M	SD	I
1. I design class activities that connect lessons to students’ daily lives.	4.51	0.65	Always
2. I integrate local culture and traditions into my lessons (stories, texts, examples).	4.37	0.74	Always
3. I use real-life examples from the students’ environment to explain concepts.	4.71	0.57	Always
4. I link lessons to real-life applications (projects, problem-solving tasks).	4.69	0.57	Always
5. I use locally available materials and teaching aids in daily teaching.	4.43	0.70	Always
6. I integrate local or real-life context to design assessments (situational tests, performance, tasks, projects).	4.57	0.64	Always
7. I incorporate current events or community issues into classroom discussions.	4.49	0.72	Always
8. I adapt my instructional strategies to align with learners’ experiences and diverse needs.	4.55	0.66	Always

9. I involve students in fieldwork or community engagement as part of lessons.	4.36	0.82	Always
10. I use peer teaching and group activities where students exchange their contextual knowledge and experience.	4.53	0.69	Always
OVERALL MEAN	4.52		Always

The results revealed that teachers always implement contextualized instructional strategies, with an overall mean of 4.52. The highest weighted mean of 4.71 was “use real-life examples from students’ environment to explain concepts, followed by “link lessons to real-life applications such as projects and problem-solving tasks with a mean of 4.69. Meanwhile, the lowest weighted mean of 4.36 was “involve students in fieldwork or community engagement as part of lessons” and “integrate local culture and traditions into my lessons” with a mean of 4.37. Overall, teachers’ strategies are both useful and manageable in the classroom, while some areas are more challenging to implement because they require additional time, coordination, and resources.

These findings were connected in the study of Ocampo and Macayan (2022), which found that project-based and real-life applications are the most common forms of contextualization due to their practicality and effectiveness. Conversely, fieldwork or community engagement, and integrating local culture and traditions were related to the study of Leung (2021), highlighted that limited administrative and resource support hinders community engagement and cultural integration.

Table 2. Significant Differences in High School Teachers’ Perceptions When Grouped by Educational Attainment and Years of Service Using Two-Way ANOVA

Source of Variation	f-value	Sig.(p)	Decision	Remarks
Educational Attainment	0.461	0.632	Accepted H ₀	Not Significant
Years of Experience	0.076	0.973	Accepted H ₀	Not Significant
Educational Attainment x Years of Service	0.785	0.504	Accepted H ₀	Not Significant
<i>Note: Significant at p < 0.05.</i>				

The results of the Two-Way ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in high school teachers’ perceptions of contextualized instructional strategies when grouped by educational attainment and years of service; therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. In other words, whether a high school teacher has a bachelor’s, master’s, or doctoral degree, or whether they are new to or not in the teaching profession, their perceptions remain consistent. This also confirmed that no combined effect between education and experience that changes these perceptions. This suggests that teachers’ favorable views on contextualization are shaped more by shared professional realities and curriculum expectations than by individual characteristics.

These findings were similarly connected in the study of Guadalupe (2024) emphasized that teachers' perceptions are strongly influenced by institutional demands and collective teaching contexts, while Diago and Dillo (2022) noted that demographic differences, such as education and tenure, often play a lesser role compared to systemic requirements like DepEd's K to 12 and MATATAG reforms.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between High School Teachers' Practices of Contextualized Instructional Strategies and Frequency of Implementation

Source of Variation	Pearson r	Sig.(p)	Decision	Remarks
Frequency of Implementation and Total Mean of Practices	0.903	<0.001	Rejected Ho	Very Significant
<i>Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)</i>				

The correlation results showed a very significant positive relationship between high school teachers' practices of contextualized instructional strategies and how often they implement these practices; therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that the more teachers value and apply contextualized instructional strategies, the more these become part of their daily teaching routines.

These findings mirrored the study of Ocampo and Macayan (2022), which showed that teachers' positive views and practices of contextualization were closely linked, indicating that what teachers believe may strongly influence what they actually do in the classroom.

4. Challenges in Implementing Contextualized Instructional Strategies

This section explores challenges identified by teachers in implementing contextualized instructional strategies, including learner diversity, lack of training/preparation, time and workload constraints, resource limitations, and subject-specific difficulty. The results drawn from the qualitative interview responses, provided that these reflect both classroom realities and systematic issues.

4.1. Learner Diversity

One of the most common challenges teachers mentioned was learner diversity. The results stated that their students come from different backgrounds, have unique learning styles, and perform at varying ability levels. As two teachers said:

- *“Students have different backgrounds, learning styles, and abilities, making it difficult to design strategies that effectively cater to everyone.” (T#1)*
- *“Having different strands makes it difficult to contextualize the activities for a single lesson in a day.” (T#47)*

In other words, contextualized instructional strategies may work for some students but not be effective for others, especially for a large class size with different students' needs and interests. A diverse classrooms make contextualization more complicated because no single approach can meet all learners' needs at once (Guadalupe, 2024).

4.2. Lack of Training and Preparation

Many teachers also expressed that they do not always feel fully equipped to apply contextualized strategies due to a lack of proper training or preparation, which often leaves them ineffective in adapting the strategies. Some teachers explained:

- *“Without proper training, it's hard to adapt strategies to the classroom context effectively.”* (T#9)
- *“Mostly lack of training or exposure on how to effectively contextualize strategies.”* (T#11)

In this case, many rely on improvisation, which may lead to inconsistency. Similarly, Tica-a and Wangdali (2023) stated that without structured professional development, teachers face difficulties in carrying out contextualized instruction consistently and confidently.

4.3. Time and Workload Constraints

Another challenge that was frequently raised by teachers was the heavy workload that they faced. Preparing and implementing contextualized instructional strategies takes extra time and effort. Two respondents admitted that:

- *“The major challenge I encounter with contextualized teaching strategies is figuring out how to create them. As a teacher, the work isn't just teaching students; it also involves creating paperwork and so on. I sometimes feel burned out, especially when I have to create contextualized and localized lesson plans every day.”* (T#37)
- *“It is more time-consuming. There's also a difficulty in thinking of differentiated activities/instructional strategies, especially when you are handling different strands. In my case, I am handling four (4) different strands”* (T#86)

This is the reality that even if teachers believe and practice contextualization, they sometimes struggle to balance it with many other tasks to accomplish. These findings were observed in the study of Bautista and Dizon (2022), that workload and limited class time often prevent teachers from fully embracing innovative instructional approaches like contextualization.

4.4. Resource Limitations

Teachers also stressed the lack of appropriate resources for contextualized instruction as a major challenge. They commented that contextualized teaching requires localized instructional materials, community-based examples, and sometimes additional teaching aids, which are often unavailable. As one teacher mentioned:

- *“Major challenges in contextualizing instructional strategies include a lack of relevant, accessible, and diverse learning materials and resources...”* (T#49)
- *“One of the major challenges I encounter when contextualizing instructional strategies is the limitation of resources. At times, I want to design meaningful, hands-on, and localized activities,*

but the lack of materials, technology, or community support hinders me from fully carrying out my plans..." (T#8)

In the absence of these, teachers fall back on generic materials that may not connect well with students' experiences. Leung (2021) argued that this lack of institutional support and localized materials limits the effectiveness of contextualized and culturally responsive instruction.

4.5. Subject-Specific Difficulty

Lastly, some teachers pointed out that contextualized instructional strategy was harder in certain subjects, particularly Mathematics and Science, because these subjects were more focused on abstract concepts that can't be directly applied to real-life contexts. Some teachers explained:

- *"Sometimes Mathematics subject is hard to relate to real-world situations or to a student's own experiences." (T#5)*
- *"As a science major handling a science subject, it is most often hard to integrate applications of the lessons to the learner's daily lives..." (T#27)*

By contrast, subjects like Araling Panlipunan or Filipino naturally lend themselves to real-world applications. Diago and Dillo (2022) also observed that technical and scientific subjects are much harder to contextualize compared to the social sciences.

5. Possible Solutions to Address Challenges about Contextualized Instructional Strategies

This section presents the possible suggested by teachers to address the challenges they encounter in implementing contextualized instructional strategies. Their responses highlight the need for professional development, provision of resources, collaboration and sharing, innovative practices, and administrative or policy support. These solutions point to a comprehensive school professional development program (SPDP) supported by the school.

5.1. Professional Development

Teachers need professional development as one of the most common solutions to address the challenges. Many felt that ongoing seminars or training would help them strengthen their skills and gain strategies. As some teachers noted:

- *"Provide more workshops and seminars in contextualized teaching strategies." (T#16)*
- *"To overcome my challenges, I need ongoing training and support to improve my teaching skills..." (T#83)*

This showed that teachers need support to do contextualized instructional strategies effectively, since they are willing to embrace the strategy. Similarly, professional development is essential for teachers' confidence and ensuring consistency in applying innovative instructional practices (Tica-a and Wangdali, 2023).

5.2. Provision of Resources

Providing enough resources for many teachers was important. They explained that contextualization requires localized materials, teaching materials, and community-based references, which are frequently lacking. Some teachers shared:

- *“To address the challenge on the limitation of resources, schools and teachers need more support through adequate teaching tools, resource-sharing, and stronger partnerships with the community.” (T#9)*
- *“...provide repositories of contextualized modules, lesson exemplars, and teaching aids relevant to learners' culture and environment.” (T#112)*

Without such support, many teachers frequently rely on their own efforts to contextualize strategies. Leung (2021) suggested that institutions must provide accessible, contextualized resources because they serve as a foundation for meaningful and culturally relevant instruction.

5.3. Collaboration and Sharing

Another solution that teachers suggested was collaboration and sharing with co-teachers. Many teachers felt that sharing best practices and experiences could ease the burden of contextualized instructional strategies. Two teachers mentioned:

- *“...mentoring, and collaborative planning with colleagues can help teachers design lessons and strategies that connect to students' real-life contexts.” (T#30)*
- *“Peer collaboration per department or among teachers teaching the same strand to lessen the burden...” (T#87)*

This shows that many teachers value professional learning groups in which they can support one another. Bautista and Dizon (2022) found that teacher collaboration reduces workload stress and promotes innovation, particularly when institutional support is lacking.

5.4. Innovative Practices

Some teachers suggested using innovative practices to make contextualization more manageable, which include the use of multimedia that makes lessons more interesting and relevant to students. Two teachers mentioned:

- *“By using technology for visual representations and incorporating interactive tools.” (T#5)*
- *“My solution in this situation, I gave them real-life examples or watch them a video to relate themselves...” (T#207)*

These statements aligned with Ocampo and Macayan (2022), who found that teachers who integrate innovation into their pedagogy are better able to bridge theory and practice in contextualized instruction.

5.5. Administrative Support

Lastly, teachers emphasized that a strong support system from school administrators was important to make contextualization sustainable. Some teachers stated:

- “...supportive administration that understands teaching challenges would also help me perform better.” (T#83)
- “School heads should encourage innovation and provide resources.” (T#178)

This viewpoint of teachers was similar to the study of Guadalupe (2024), that without administrative support, contextualized strategies, risk becomes inconsistent and dependent only on individual teacher initiative.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

The study was conducted only within one school setting which limits the generalizability of the findings to other schools with different teaching conditions, and resources. The experiences and perceptions of teachers in other schools might differ depending on their institutional support and student diversity.

The qualitative portion was limited to open-ended survey responses and suggested an in-depth interview or focus group discussions that provide a more complete picture of this study. Despite these limitations, the findings still provide valuable insights into teachers’ real experiences and perceptions, serving as a foundation for further research.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Teachers strongly believe that contextualized instructional strategies help students to improve their learning and engagement; however, integration of culture and indigenous knowledge needs further consideration.
2. Teachers’ perceptions of contextualized instructional strategies are positive and consistent, regardless of their educational attainment and years of service.
3. The strong positive relationship between practices and frequency of implementation reflects that teachers value contextualized instructional strategies and are more likely to apply them in their lessons.
4. Teachers are experiencing challenges despite positive perceptions in the implementation, such as learner diversity, lack of training and preparation, time and workload constraints, resource limitations, and subject-specific difficulty.
5. Teachers are suggesting the need for a stronger administrative support through professional development, provision of resources, and collaboration with colleagues that sustain the improvement of contextualized instructional strategies.

The researchers concluded that the respondents confirmed that contextualized instructional strategies are both valued and consistently practiced, regardless of their profile. For the betterment of the results, the

researchers suggested for the school administrators the preparation of the School Professional Development Program to address the challenges and concerns.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. Teachers should encourage the use of real-life examples and experiences to make learning more meaningful and relevant for the students, as well as consider using project-based and hands-on activities that can help students connect lessons to the environment around them.
2. Teachers should also collaborate and share effective strategies and practices, and develop contextualized learning materials together through Professional Learning Communities (PLCs), so that teachers can lighten their workload.
3. School administrators should develop and implement a School Professional Development Program (SPDP) to support teachers in contextualized strategies, so that teachers may deepen their understanding and skills. This program may include:
 - a. Capacity-building workshops that help teachers learn how to contextualize lessons, integrate culture, and use innovative strategies for hard-to-contextualize subjects;
 - b. Development of digital and printed contextualized materials;
 - c. Peer observation, mentoring, and sharing sessions that foster collaboration and reflective practices; and
 - d. Community engagement projects that help teachers connect classroom lessons with the local environment.
4. School administrators may invite DepEd master teachers as speakers who specialize in contextualized instructional strategies.
5. DepEd and policymakers should promote contextualized instruction in private schools, particularly in terms of resource allocation and curriculum flexibility. Include private school teachers in the teacher induction and continuing professional development (CPD) programs that integrate contextualization training.
6. Expanding this study to include all private school teachers who participated in the conducted survey is highly recommended.

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